

Cognitive edge-cloud with serverless computing

The second year of the EDGELESS project started with a team gathering, laying the foundation for a successful year ahead filled with dedication and accomplishments. Additionally, EDGELESS made notable appearances at various events, notably LESS'24, where mini interviews were conducted with experts such as Chiara Boldrini, Pablo Serrano, Franca Delmastro, Lorenzo Valerio, Cristina L. Abad, and Carlo Vallati.

In this newsletter, we proudly present a recap of the past three months' achievements as well as what is coming up! Enjoy and don't forget to follow us online (if you are not doing it already), for more immediate updates!

Our Latest Highlights

EDGELESS 2nd Plenary Meeting

The EDGELESS plenary meeting took place on January 30th and 31st, 2024, in Braunschweig, Germany. Hosted by our esteemed partner, AEGIS, the gathering provided a valuable opportunity for all partners to come together and reflect on the progress made in Year One while setting the stage for continued success in Year Two.

EDGELESS at LESS'24

The 3rd edition of the workshop series on Serverless Computing for Pervasive Cloud-Edge-Device Systems and Services (*LESS) was held on March 11, 2024 in Biarritz, France, co-located with the International IEEE Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications (PerCom).

EDGELESS Videos

In this short demonstration we show the creation of multiple workflows, each consisting of a single function, whose instances are created on two edge computing devices hosting an EDGELESS node with a WebAssembly runner

Interview of Chiara Boldrini in Biarritz at the 22nd International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications (PerCom 2024). She provides her opinion on how initiatives such as the EDGELESS project can increase the appeal of serverless for the pervasive computing research community.

Interview of Pablo Serrano in Biarritz at the 22nd International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications (PerCom 2024). He discusses the most appealing features of serverless for the research community of pervasive computing and the biggest threat to the adoption of serverless in this community.

Interview of Franca Delmastro in Biarritz at the 22nd International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications (PerCom 2024). Franca provides her opinion on what is the biggest challenge to be addressed by the research community to make a significant impact on real-life applications.

EDGELESS Videos

Interview of Lorenzo Valerio in Biarritz at the 22nd International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications (PerCom 2024). Lorenzo discusses the most critical technology barriers to the use of resource-constrained devices.

Interview of Cristina L. Abad in Biarritz at the 22nd International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications (PerCom 2024). She provides her opinion on the future of serverless computing in small edge computing devices.

Interview of Carlo Vallati in Biarritz at the 22nd International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications (PerCom 2024). Carlo is an associate professor at the University of Pisa, where he coordinates the Cloud Computing, Big Data, and Cybersecurity laboratory (Crosslab).

Visit [EDGELESS YouTube Channel](#)

Our Latest Articles

EDGELESS Monitoring System

EDGELESS integrates monitoring as a critical component of its overall system architecture. The purpose of monitoring within EDGELESS is to enable real-time data distribution and dynamic resource optimization.

Serverless computing: Leveraging the use of Hardware Secure Modules

Serverless computing represents a shift in the deployment of applications and services, as computation and data storage are brought closer to the users, saving bandwidth and improving response times.

Simplifying Edge Computing Orchestration via Oakestra

Understanding the Basics: What is Edge computing and Orchestration?
How Oakestra Operates: The Technical Rundown.

CONSORTIUM

The project unites **12 partners** from **6 European countries**, encompassing the necessary expertise to successfully accomplish the project's ambitious goals.

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